

PERCEPTION OF TEACHERS ON INDISCIPLINE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN OSUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

Indiscipline in school greatly affects the quality of teaching and learning which results to poor results, dropouts, and wastage of resources invested by stakeholders of education such as parents, and the government. The study made use of descriptive survey research design; and it was guided by five research questions and three research hypotheses. A sample size of 200 teachers was drawn by stratified sampling technique from three local educational zones in Osun State using six public and four private secondary schools. The instrument tagged " Perception of Teachers on Students' Indiscipline in Nigerian Secondary Schools" (PTSINSS) was adapted and validated by two experts in Test and Measurement and Counselling Psychology. The test-retest reliability co-efficient of the instrument was 0.84. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics such as percentage, mean, t- value and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The study showed that there is a significant difference between male and female teachers' perception on school-based factors that causes indiscipline of secondary school students in Osun State. There is a significant difference between school-based and societal-based factors that causes indiscipline in secondary schools as perceived by teachers in Osun State; and teachers' years of experience do not significantly influence the possible solutions to curb students' indiscipline. In conclusion, indiscipline of students could lead to closure of schools, wanton destruction of property, corruption of differ kinds, moral decadence and loss of lives. The parents, school authorities, the society and the government should take proactive measures against this social menace by ensuring that good behaviour and conditions are inculcated, established and maintained for effective learning in schools.

Keywords: indiscipline, teachers, cultism, bullying, drug abuse

1. Introduction

Indiscipline is the breaking of rules and regulations of institutions. Individuals willingly or unwillingly violating laid down rules of an institution, which hampers the smooth running of the institution. Indiscipline can simply be seen as mode of life NOT in conformity with rules and non-subjection to control. By extension, the term indiscipline connotes the violations of school rules and regulations capable of obstructing the smooth and orderly functioning of the school system. Indiscipline breeds corruption and other related social vices (Jekayinfa (2013). Zubaida (2009) identifies various forms of indiscipline among the secondary school students such as truancy, lateness to school, cultism, drug abuse, insulting/assaulting, stealing, rioting, and many other antisocial vices. According to him, a number of these acts of indiscipline were directed against constituted authorities and established rules. An example of this is refusal to wear the right school uniform and going out of bounds without permission. The respect which teachers command among students had been seriously worn-off. And some teachers have not done much to help the situation by their actions.

Onyije and Ojedapo (2010) identify some factors that cause indiscipline among students such as government nonchalant attitudes to education, parental factors and teachers' attitude. Student indiscipline is a great concern among education administrators, teachers and stakeholders across the globe (Njoroge & Nyabuto, 2014). Student insurgences against authority are increasing in most countries, perhaps because nowadays schools have children from dysfunctional homes, poverty stricken, single parents or teenage parents (Kute, 2014). Parental supervision is also declining day by day causing many students to develop low regard towards all forms of authority. Schools today have to deal with the problem of weapons, recruitment into criminal groups, rivalry, drugs and substance abuse, trafficking and youth radicalization. These cases are experienced all over the world (Afullo, 2005; Kute, 2014). The problem of indiscipline in schools has persisted over the years. These acts have either been carried out individually by the students or as a group which result to rioting or revolts (Idu & Ojedapo, 2011).

There are many types of indiscipline behaviours exhibited by students in secondary schools. For instance, Hamza in Odiba (2006), identified basically three types of indiscipline in schools which include Anti social act; Act of defiance and Act of negligence. Anti social act refers to the destruction of public properties and rioting, hooliganism, stealing and bullying. Act of defiance can usually be directed against established rules of the school for instance, going out without permission, avoidance of wearing school uniform, smoking, drinking of alcohol and abuse of drugs, sexual immorality and failure to serve punishment and carry out lawful duties while acts of negligence are many which include lateness to school and careless handling of school facilities.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Indiscipline in secondary schools in Nigeria has caused so many problems by devaluating our certificates through examination malpractice and certificate forgery; wanton destruction of school and government properties through violence; and killing and maiming themselves through drug and substance abuse and cultism. Indiscipline in school greatly affects the quality of teaching and learning which results to poor results, dropouts, and wastage of resources invested by stakeholders of education such as parents, and the government. Against this background, the study was carried out to investigate the causes, types, and possible ways to curb indiscipline in schools from principals, vice principals teachers, parents and students.

1.2 Research Questions

1. What are the most frequent types of students' indiscipline in secondary schools in Osun State?
2. What are the students-based causes that trigger students' indiscipline in secondary schools in Osun State?
3. What are the school-based factors that cause indiscipline in secondary schools in Osun State?
4. What are the societal-based factors that cause indiscipline in secondary schools in Osun State?
5. What are the possible solutions to curb the identified causes of indiscipline in secondary schools in Osun State?

1.3 Research Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the perception of male and female teachers on school based factors that cause indiscipline in secondary schools.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between schools and societal based factors that causes indiscipline in secondary schools.

HO₃: Teachers years of experience do not significantly influence the possible solutions to curb students' indiscipline in secondary schools.

2. Research Design

The research method used was the descriptive survey. The researchers utilized survey method because the study investigates perception of teachers to indiscipline among secondary school students as perceived by teachers.

2.1 Population of the Study

The study covered all the public secondary schools in Ife Central, Ife East and Ife South local government areas of Osun State.

2.2 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample of this study consisted of 200 teachers. The sample was drawn through stratified sampling technique from three local educational zones in Osun State, which were Ife Central, Ife East and Ife South Educational Zones. Six public and four private secondary schools were randomly selected from the three educational zones, while 20 teachers were randomly selected from each of the 10 schools.

2.3 Instrumentation

The instrument tagged "Perception of Teachers on Students' Indiscipline in Osun State Secondary Schools" (PTSIOSSS) was adapted from Ponfua (2015). The survey instrument has four sections, which include personal data, 9 question items on students' indiscipline in schools, 18 question items on major causes of students' indiscipline in Nigerian secondary schools, and 11 question items relating to possible solutions to curb students' indiscipline in Nigerian secondary schools. It was a 4-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. Responses were assigned values ranging from 4-1 points.

2.4 Validation of the Instrument

The instrument "PTSINSS" was subjected to content and face validity by two experts in the area of Test and Measurement and Counselling Psychology from Faculty of Education, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife.

2.5 Reliability of the Instrument

Test-retest method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. After the first administration of the instrument, an interval of three weeks was reached before the second administration. A correlation coefficient of 0.84 was reached.

2.6 Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, mean, rank, t-value analysis, and ANOVA

3. Results

Research Question 1: What are the most frequent types of students' indiscipline in secondary schools as perceived by teachers in Osun State?

Table 1: Mean and Rank order analysis on most frequent types of students' indiscipline in secondary schools as perceived by teachers in Osun State

S/N	Types of Students' Indiscipline	Mean	Rank
1	Assault and insults on teachers and non-teachers	2.75	6 th
2	Assault on school prefects	2.88	2 nd
3	Vandalism	2.98	1 st
4	Mass protest	2.56	8 th

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5	Cultism	2.77	5 th
6	Wearing dirty and wrong uniform	2.67	7 th
7	Drug abuse and alcoholism	2.83	3 rd
8	Examination malpractice	2.55	9 th
9	Fighting	2.82	4 th

From Table 1, the most frequent types of students indiscipline as perceived by teachers in rank order are vandalism, assault on school prefects, drug abuse and alcoholism, fighting, cultism, assault and insult on teachers and non-teachers, wearing dirty and wrong uniform, mass protest and examination malpractice.

Research Question 2: What are the students-based causes that trigger students' indiscipline in secondary schools in Osun State?

Table 2: Mean and Rank order analysis on students based causes that trigger students indiscipline in as perceived by secondary school teachers in Osun State

S/N	Students based factor	Mean	Rank
1	Low self-concept due to constant negative label	2.76	4 th
2	Abuse of seniority by prefects	3.00	1 st
3	Poor study habits	2.56	5 th
4	Restlessness and inattention	2.89	3 rd
5	Bullying	2.99	2 nd

From Table 2, the students' based-factors that trigger students' indiscipline as perceived by teachers in rank order are abuse of seniority by prefects, bullying, restlessness and inattention, low self-concept due to constant negative label and poor study habits.

Research Question 3: What are the schools-based factors that cause indiscipline in secondary schools in Osun State?

Table 3: Mean and Rank order analysis on students-based factors that trigger students' indiscipline in secondary schools as perceived by teachers in Osun State

S/N	School-based factors	Mean	Rank
6	Harsh school rules and regulations	2.99	1 st
7	Unconducive school environment	2.58	6 th
8	Poor leadership of some school administrators	2.87	3 rd
9	Lack of extra-curricular activities	2.92	2 nd
10	Poor teaching of some teachers	2.52	7 th
11	Teachers lateness and absenteeism	2.66	5 th
12	Overcrowded classrooms	2.68	4 th

From Table 3, the school-based factors that trigger students indiscipline as perceived by teachers in rank order are harsh school rules and regulations, lack of extra- curricular activities, poor leadership of some school administrators, overcrowded classrooms,

teachers lateness and absenteeism, uncondusive school environment and poor teaching of some teachers.

Research Question 4: What are the societal-based factors that cause indiscipline in secondary schools in Osun State?

Table 4: Mean and Rank order analysis on societal-based factors that trigger students as perceived by teachers in Osun State

S/N	Societal-based factors	Mean	Rank
13	Poor value system	2.77	2 nd
14	Injustice in the society revealed by favourism, nepotism and corruption	2.68	5 th
15	Unwholesome mass media	2.58	6 th
16	Unsatisfactory home condition in some families	2.76	3 rd
17	Parental over protection of children	2.66	4 th
18	Parental rejection of children	2.95	1 st

From Table 4, the rank order analysis on societal-based factors that trigger students as perceived by teachers are poor value system, injustice in the society revealed by favourism, nepotism and corruption unwholesome mass media, unsatisfactory home condition in some families, parental over protection and rejection of children.

Research Question 5: What are the possible solutions to curb the identified causes of indiscipline in secondary schools in Osun State?

Table 5: Mean and Rank order analysis on possible solutions to curb the identified causes of indiscipline in secondary schools as perceived by teachers in Osun State

S/N	Possible Solutions to curb students indiscipline	Mean	Rank
1	Moral leadership and education	2.86	3 rd
2	School authorities to be of good models	2.99	1 st
3	Provision of adequate facilities for teaching, games and sports	2.66	10 th
4	Involvement of students in making rules and regulations	2.67	9 th
5	Reduction of class size	2.77	7 th
6	Value orientation	2.88	2 nd
7	Effective Parents Teachers Association (PTA)	2.83	4 th
8	Emphasis on extracurricular activities	2.56	11 th
9	Positive teacher/students relationship	2.68	8 th
10	Provision of ICTs and internet in schools	2.78	6 th
11	High parental and school supervision and counseling	2.79	5 th

From Table 5, the rank order analysis of possible solutions to curb indiscipline in secondary schools as perceived by teachers in Osun State are school authorities to be of good models, value orientation, moral leadership and education, effective Parents and Teachers Association (PTA), high parental and school supervision counseling, provision of ICT and internet in schools, reduction of class size, positive teachers/students relationship, involvement of students in making rules and regulations, provision of

adequate facilities for teaching, games and sports and emphasis on extracurricular activities.

3.1 Hypothesis Testing

In this study, null hypotheses were formulated and tested using t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistical procedure. Significant difference was determined at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the perception of male and female teachers' on school based factors that cause indiscipline in secondary schools.

Table 6: Mean, Standard Deviation, and t-test of respondents view on the basis of gender

Gender	N	$\bar{x}$	SD	df	Calculated t-value	Critical t-value	Decision
Male	109	27.51	3.18	198	2.052	1.96	Rejected
Female	91	27.54	3.10				

*Significant: P < 0.05

Table 6 above shows the mean, Standard Deviation, and the t-value of respondents on the basis of gender. The result revealed that the calculated t-value of 2.052 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.96 with 198 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance, thus null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between male and female teachers' perception on school-based factors that causes indiscipline of secondary school students in Osun State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between school and societal based factors that causes indiscipline in secondary schools

Table 7: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-value of teachers view between school-based and societal-based factors that causes indiscipline

Gender	N	$\bar{x}$	SD	df	Calculated t-value	Critical t-value	Decision
School factors	120	27.56	3.20	198	3.252	1.96	Rejected
Societal factors	80	27.50	3.12				

*Significant: P < 0.05

Table 7 above shows the mean, Standard Deviation, and t-value of respondents' on the basis of factors based. The result of the Table revealed that the calculated t-value of 3.252 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.96 with 198 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance, thus null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between school-based and societal-based factors that causes indiscipline in secondary schools as perceived by teachers in Osun State.

Hypothesis 3: Teachers years of experience do not significantly influence the possible solutions to curb students' indiscipline in secondary schools.

Table 8: ANOVA comparing respondents' years of experience to possible solutions to curb students indiscipline

Source	Df	SS	Calculated F-value	Critical F-value	Decision
Between Group	4	22.101	1.499	2.37	Accepted
Within Group	195	2157.774			
Total	199	2179.875			

*Significant: $P < 0.05$

Table 8 above presents the calculated F-value of 1.499 which is greater than the critical F-value of 2.37 at 0.05 alpha levels, thus the hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference. Teachers' years of experience do not significantly influence the possible solutions to curb students' indiscipline.

4. Discussion

The study showed that the most frequent types of students indiscipline as perceived by teachers in rank order were vandalism, assault on school prefects, drug abuse and alcoholism, fighting, cultism, assault and insult on teachers and non-teachers, wearing dirty and wrong uniform, mass protest and examination malpractice. This finding corroborated the reports of Reid (2000), Ebontane (2006) and Ponfua (2015) who reported violence and insubordination to administrative staff, teachers and school prefects among secondary school students in Cameroon, Chicago, New York, Washington and Detroit

The findings on the students' based-factors that trigger students' indiscipline as perceived by teachers in rank order were abuse of seniority by prefects, bullying, restlessness and inattention, low self-concept due to constant negative label and poor study habits. This finding supported the result of Ponfua (2015) that constant negative labels on students, abuse of seniority by school prefects, students poor study habits and students' restlessness and inattention in class were the major factors.

The study revealed that the school-based factors that trigger students indiscipline as perceived by teachers were harsh school rules and regulations, lack of extra- curricular activities, poor leadership of some school administrators, overcrowded classrooms, teachers lateness and absenteeism, unconducive school environment and poor teaching of some teachers.ve for long tends to make them inattentive in class and restless. This finding corroborated the studies of Asiyai (2005), Yaroson, 2006 and Ponfua (2015) who identified the unrealistic rules, unconducive school environment characterized by acute shortage of facilities for teaching, games and sports that trigger indiscipline

The study found that societal-based factors that trigger students' indiscipline as perceived by teachers were poor value system, injustice in the society revealed by favourism, nepotism and corruption, unwholesome mass media, unsatisfactory home condition in some families, and parental over protection and rejection of children. This observation was in line with the studies of Abduhamid and Yaduma (2007), Danso (2010) and Ponfua (2015), who noted that hard work is jettisoned while favouritism and nepotism become the order of the day. Unsatisfactory home condition breeds in children a feeling of insecurity and frustration and thus contributing to the formation of deviant behaviour which they manifest at school. In addition, the dynamic explosion of the mass media system through television, magazines and computer have contributed to the inculcation of deviant practices among most students.

The findings on the possible solutions to curb indiscipline in secondary schools include school authorities to be of good models, value orientation, moral leadership and education, effective Parents and Teachers Association (PTA), high parental and school supervision counseling, provision of ICT and internet in schools, reduction of class size, positive teachers/students relationship, involvement of students in making rules and regulations, provision of adequate facilities for teaching, games and sports and emphasis on extracurricular activities. This finding was similar to Ponfua (2015).

The result of the hypothesis one revealed that there was a significant difference between male and female teachers' perception on school-based factors that causes indiscipline of secondary school students in Osun State.

The finding of hypothesis two showed that there was a significant difference between school-based and societal-based factors that causes indiscipline in secondary schools as perceived by teachers in Osun State.

The result of hypothesis three revealed that teachers' years of experience do not significantly influence the possible solutions to curb students' indiscipline.

5. Conclusion

From this study, the factors that trigger indiscipline could be students, school or societal based. Indiscipline of students could lead to closure of schools, wanton destruction of property, corruption of differ kinds, moral decadence and loss of lives. The parents, school authorities, the society and the government should take proactive measures against this social menace by ensuring that good behaviour and conditions are inculcated, established and maintained for effective learning in schools.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made.

- The government, policy makers, education reformers and school administrators should ensure that schools are provided with adequate facilities for teaching and

learning, sports and games as well as information communication technologies and internet connectivity.

- The mass and electronic media should be used to enlighten all stakeholders in the areas investigated on the effect of indiscipline in the society.
- School curriculum should emphasize moral education for good character training.
- Parents, the school and religious bodies that are charged with moral training of children should ensure that sound moral education is given to children.
- There should be reward for good conduct and punishment for bad conduct at home, school and society at large by parents, teachers and government.
- All schools should have a competent professional Guidance Counselor.

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